

Abstract

EnzymeML has been designed as an SBML-based exchange format for data on enzyme-catalyzed reactions. It integrates experimental data such as time course of substrates or products and metadata on the enzyme and the reaction conditions with modelling data such as the kinetic model and the kinetic parameters obtained by fitting of the time course data by the kinetic model. Thus, EnzymeML makes data and metadata related to a biocatalytic experiment findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (Wilkinson 2016). Most of the biocatalytic data is described by SBML (Hucka et al., 2018) and is enriched by MIRIAM (Novère et al., 2005) annotation and by additional EnzymeML annotations, the SBML file is included into a Combine Archive, which includes additionally the original data on which basis the modeling is made. In EnzymeML the structure of the experiment and the modeling part are separated in different SBML files. This allows the reuse of the same data for different modeling approaches to identify the parameters of the model.

EnzymeML is designed to help the experimenters with a standardized file format, which is based on current standards to easily write, model and publish results of biocatalytic experiments. While experimenters can parse their manual designed experiment tables into EnzymeML, the container file can be used to model the experiment directly in a modeling platform with the attached experiment data. All the results can be published then on different platforms, because EnzymeML contains the most relevant data which is needed by other scientist to do their research.

Figure 1: EnzymeML as an exchange format
EnzymeML serves as the exchange format for the FAIR principles of biocatalytic data. It aims to give the experimenter the opportunity, to create interoperable and reusable data. The data can then be used for modelling and publication purposes.

Figure 2: Application of EnzymeML
EnzymeML will be applied by the experimenter through spreadsheet programs with templates. Those templates can then be used to create EnzymeML files automatically with scripts.

```
<enzymeml:data xmlns:enzymeml="www.enzymeml.org/enzymeml/version1/core">
  <enzymeml:listOfFormats>
    <enzymeml:format id="format0">
      <enzymeml:column type="time" unit="seconds"/>
      <enzymeml:column type="conc" species="s0" replica="repl0" unit="u0"/>
      <enzymeml:column type="conc" species="s1" replica="repl0" unit="u0"/>
      <enzymeml:column type="empty"/>
      <enzymeml:column type="conc" species="s0" replica="repl1" unit="u0"/>
      <enzymeml:column type="conc" species="s1" replica="repl1" unit="u0"/>
    </enzymeml:format>
  </enzymeml:listOfFormats>
  <enzymeml:listOfFiles>
    <enzymeml:file id="file0" file="measures.csv" format="format0"/>
  </enzymeml:listOfFiles>
  <enzymeml:listOfMeasurements>
    <enzymeml:measurement id="M0" file="file0" name="of date DD/MM/YY" start="2" stop="52"/>
    <enzymeml:measurement id="M1" file="file0" name="of date DD/MM/YY" start="53" stop="103"/>
  </enzymeml:listOfMeasurements>
</enzymeml:data>
```

Figure 4: Structuring the CSV files
The CSV files with the measurement data can be organized freely. The format gives the structure of the specific CSV file and is attached to all the files that follow this concept. The addition of the measurement list allows to store different replicas in one file, while giving the flexibility to use different time stamps and storing it horizontally or vertically.

```
<enzymeml:reaction xmlns:enzymeml="www.enzymeml.org/enzymeml/version1/core">
  <enzymeml:conditions>
    <enzymeml:ph value="7.2"/>
    <enzymeml:temperature unit="kelvin" value="273.16"/>
    <enzymeml:pressure unit="kPa" value="101.0"/>
  </enzymeml:conditions>
  <enzymeml:replicas>
    <enzymeml:replica id="re1" measurement="M0" replica="repl0"/>
    <enzymeml:replica id="re2" measurement="M0" replica="repl1"/>
    <enzymeml:replica id="re3" measurement="M1" replica="repl0"/>
    <enzymeml:replica id="re4" measurement="M1" replica="repl1"/>
  </enzymeml:replicas>
</enzymeml:reaction>
```

Figure 5: Structuring the reaction annotations
The reaction element stores the information about the conditions of the experiment and lists the replicas that contain data about this reaction for later parameter estimations.

Figure 3: The structure of the file format
The EnzymeML file is structured as a Combine Archive (Bergmann 2014) data container. The heart of the file is the experiment SBML file. This includes data about the experiment and further annotations to be findable and reusable. The data of the experiments is saved in attached CSV files and is referred to by the experiment file. The model files are used for the modelling part of the experiment and use the attached data for it.

For a discussion on how to apply EnzymeML in biocatalysis, please visit the poster by **Stephan Malzacher** :
“Enhancing the computational based function annotation of thiamine diphosphate dependent enzymes.”

References

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